

ON THE COMPETENCE OF PROGRAMMING ANIMATED LINEAR CURVATURE MODELS TO PRINT

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This study explores how students conceptualize mathematical ideas related to curvature and rate of change, and develop mathematical competence through 3D design, programming, and physical modeling. Curvature is approached as a rich conceptual field for developing students' mathematical thinking through an intrinsically defined approach. Drawing on the theoretical frameworks of constructionism, reification and the KOM framework, and focusing on students' engagement with the MaLT2 programming environment, we investigate how students build and use mathematically meaningful ideas through iterative processes of 'imaging, seeing and touching'. The findings reveal educational opportunities arising from the interplay between digital and physical artifacts, especially when programming serves as a medium for design and mathematical exploration.

Keywords: Mathematical competence, curvature, programming, 3D models, 3D printing.

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional geometry has gained renewed significance in contemporary mathematics education through the integration of 3D printing technologies, prompting a re-examination of pedagogical approaches in digitally mediated learning environments (Ng et al., 2018). Designing and printing 3D models enhances student engagement by fostering creativity through authentic problem-solving and essential skills such as spatial reasoning, iterative design, testing, and reflection (Dickson et al., 2021; Coşkun & Deniz, 2022). However, research specifically exploring 3D printing's potential for mathematics learning remains limited. Most studies focus on basic geometric concepts (e.g., volume, properties of solids), STEM/STEAM approaches, or ready-made models (Huleihil, 2017). Few pedagogical approaches integrate mathematical and engineering aspects, such as coding and printing, for developing competence. Drawing on Niss & Højgaard's (2019) competence perspective, which emphasizes not only what students know but also how they know it and what they use it for, we investigate students' mathematical competence development during a design-based modelling task on curvature. This task uses the MaLT2 programming environment, which supports intrinsically defined curvature and allows dynamic manipulation and 3D printing of models. Although curvature is a fundamental concept in mathematics and applied fields, it remains absent from the Greek curriculum as a lens for exploring curves as shapes arising from covariational relations. Viewing curves dynamically allows students to perceive mathematical relationships as evolving interactions, fostering deeper conceptual understanding of curvature and preparing them for a more profound grasp of calculus (Tall 1989; Kynigos & Zantzou, 2017; Dilling & Witzke, 2020).

THEORETICAL FRAMING

Adopting a constructionist approach to our research view and task design, we aim to engage students in exploring the geometric nature of curves through designing and printing of 3D models.

Grounded in Papert's (1980) theory of constructionism, which posits that learning is most effective when students construct meaningful, personal, and shareable artefacts, this approach emphasizes student agency in generating mathematical meaning through designing, modifying, and printing their own models. While constructionism has been widely explored in mathematics education, it has not yet been linked to the emerging focus on mathematical competence (Kynigos & Schiza, 2023). Focusing solely on meanings students construct risks overlooking whether and how these meanings translate into actionable competence. While necessary, mathematical meanings alone are insufficient today. Competence entails mobilizing these meanings strategically, adaptively and insightfully across contexts, a distinction emphasized in the KOM (Competencies for Mathematics Learning) framework. Developed by Niss and Højgaard (2011; 2019), the KOM framework, widely adopted in research, outlines eight distinct yet interconnected competencies that may emerge concurrently or trigger one another, and defines mathematical competence as "*insightful readiness to act appropriately in response to all kinds of mathematical challenges pertaining to a given situation*" (2019, p. 12). Competence, in this view, extends beyond knowledge or skills, emphasizing the ability to use one's abilities effectively in context. Although the role of digital technology is not explicitly addressed in the KOM framework, significant work has recently been done on how digital media can serve mathematics education research and pedagogy (e.g., Jankvist and Geraniou, 2022). In line with this perspective, our research investigates how iterative cycles of designing, seeing and touching through programming shape students' mathematical competence in the MaLT2 tool.

When investigating students' mathematical competence, we argue that it should be examined within its broader conceptual field rather than in isolation. Following Vergnaud's (1983) notion of conceptual fields, the concept of curvature is interconnected with others, such as slope, tangent, rate of change, local geometry, limit, and derivative. In this study, we focus on findings related to the rate of change that emerged during students' design processes. Rate of change lies at the heart of mathematical and scientific literacy and is fundamental to teaching calculus. Yet, understanding this concept is far from straightforward. Numerous studies have shown that students, even in advanced stages of schooling, struggle with it despite frequent exposure to related concepts like velocity or slope. Research suggests that these difficulties are persistent and profound, leading many scholars to advocate its earlier introduction through realistic contexts and gradual transition toward formal definitions such as the derivative (Orton, 1984; Teuscher et al., 2010; Avgerinos & Remoundou, 2021). Beyond its formal definition, curvature offers a powerful ground for exploring curves as geometric entities arising from covariational relationships between quantities (Thompson, 1994). Carlson et al. (2002) argue that covariation clarifies the concept of rate of change, an intuitive property of functions, and suggest introducing it visually rather than numerically. In MaLT2, the mathematical approach to 3D shapes draws on differential geometry, where curvature is seen as an intrinsic property of curves. Our activity builds on Turtle Geometry (Papert, 1980), which expresses geometric ideas through local, constructive procedures rather than equations, making advanced concepts like curvature and rate of change more accessible to students.

While constructionism foregrounds students' agency in meaning-making through artefact creation, and the KOM framework incorporates an analytic lens shifting focus from descriptions of what students understand toward what they are ready and able to do with that understanding, we also needed a theoretical lens to trace their conceptual development; Sfard's theory of reification. According to Sfard (1991), mathematical concepts can be understood in two different ways: structurally (as objects) and operationally (as processes). Mathematics learning arises from an interaction between these two elements, and involves a progression from computational

operational to abstract objects through a series of cognitive transitions, accomplished in three stages: *interiorization*, *condensation*, and *reification*. In *interiorization*, learners engage repeatedly with a mathematical process, gradually internalizing its structure through concrete activity, still perceiving it as a sequence of actions. In *condensation*, the process is seen more holistically, enabling cognitive efficiency and mental manipulation without focusing on individual steps. *Reification* marks the transition from process to object, as the idea is reconceptualized as a manipulable entity within a broader mathematical framework, enabling higher-order thinking and further conceptual development. In our case, the coding process aligns with an operational view of curves, presenting them as computational procedures. Conversely, graphical figures and printed models support a more structural approach, portraying the curve as a unified whole. Visualization makes abstract concepts more tangible and manipulable. While learning typically begins with physical objects and moves toward abstraction, our approach works in the opposite direction: beginning with model design and culminating in physical instantiation via 3D printing. We therefore advocate for the integration of both processes as complementary tools for structuring and deepening mathematical knowledge and understanding. We argue that when mathematical concepts are too abstract or unfamiliar, they can be grasped through other ideas (e.g. spatial relations or physical objects) and repetitive cycles of imagining (coding), seeing (graphical figure) and touching (3D printed model). Taken together, these frameworks enable a multifaceted analysis: constructionism offers a pedagogical stance, reification a cognitive trajectory, and KOM a descriptive and evaluative structure; each indispensable for fully understanding how students learn through digital-physical modeling. Thus, our research is guided by the question: *“How do students conceptualize mathematical ideas related to curvature and develop mathematical competence through 3D design, programming, and physical modeling with the programmable tool MaLT2?”*

METHOD

The study involved 45 eleventh-grade students who participated in an 8-session, 10-hour intervention integrated into their curriculum, working in pairs. To foster motivation and balanced support, groups were formed with students of varying achievement levels. Both the teacher and the participating researcher acted as facilitators, promoting an open, collaborative environment. To gain a holistic view of students' actions and interpretations, we conducted thematic analysis across multiple data sources, i.e., screen and audio recordings, students' notes, MaLT2 codes, artifacts, and photographs. The analysis followed an initial coding scheme while remaining open to emerging themes. Transcribed dialogues were triangulated with the other data and analyzed based on critical episodes (Tripp, 1993); key moments in which students' meanings and actions around curvature emerged during the design and modeling task. To address our research question, we identified incidents in which students described or expressed ideas related to curvature, as well as moments in which their actions or reflections demonstrated growth in mathematical competence through the interplay of programming, visual feedback, and physical output. As the intervention constituted the second cycle of a broader design-based research project (Bakker, 2018), the findings will inform subsequent iterations and refinements of the activity.

Digital tool and design of the activity

MaLT2 (<http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/malt2/>) is a web-based programmable tool designed to support symbolic representation in mathematical tasks through textual programming. It enables the creation and exploration of 3D graphical models, offering dynamic manipulation of variables used

within procedures (Kynigos & Grizioti, 2018). The MaLT2 environment integrates three interrelated kinds of representation: (i) symbolic representation via code, (ii) visual representation through a 3D scene, and (iii) dynamic manipulation of generalized models using parametric procedures (Figure 1a). A variation tool introduces sliders for each variable in the active procedure, allowing users to adjust parameters that influence the shape of a trace. Recently, MaLT2 incorporated a 3D printing feature (<https://extendt2.com/widgets/malt/>), enabling students to link digital models with physical objects, thus supporting the development of mathematical understanding and various transversal skills (Grizioti et al., 2024). As part of a Design Thinking project on green energy, students were asked to design digital models of sustainable solutions for their municipality using the Logo-like MaLT2 environment. The activity extended beyond the digital realm, allowing students to print and interact with physical prototypes at the end of each session in order to gather feedback before producing their final artifacts. During the project's 1st cycle, students worked on the surface of a given code-based cylinder, introducing them to the concepts of torsion and local curvature (Kynigos & Schiza, 2025). In the current phase, however, researchers intentionally avoided prescribing a specific solid, allowing students more creative freedom as the cylinder was seen as potentially limiting their engagement. Instead, students were introduced to an open "half-baked" microworld (Kynigos, 2007) featuring a random curve (i.e., `repeat :n [roll_right :a up :b forward :c right :d]`) to initiate exploration and support emergent construction.

RESULTS

The research question guiding this intervention explored how students generate meanings related to curvature and how mathematics is enacted through their engagement with MaLT2 for designing, tinkering with, and 3D printing models. We begin by presenting a critical episode under the theme "Curvature conceptualization", followed by a brief analysis of the theme "Interplay of different representations". To avoid confusion, it should be noted that all student quotes and dialogue presented in both themes refer to the same group of students. The following critical incident serves as an example of how students, despite having no prior knowledge of the concept, understood curvature as rate of change and use it in their model. It also highlights the development of their mathematical competence from an operational to a structural perspective. By this stage, the group had created a wind turbine model and were working on the final curved section, having spent a long time discussing its shape, size and orientation. After several minutes of collaborative reasoning about how to achieve the desired curve, the teacher posed a clarifying question that revealed students' emerging ideas about curvature within the turtle geometry programming environment.

- 368 Student A: If there was a curvature command... designing the curve would be easier. We wouldn't need to deal with degrees.
- 369 Teacher: How exactly do you think this command would work in your model?
- 370 Student A: Pretty much the same as the 'forward' command. The difference is that instead of going straight, the path would curve; like this (hand gesture).
- 371 Student B: So basically, we are talking about curvature as a property of the 'forward'.
- 372 Student A: Yes! If we had, let's say, two commands that worked together –like 'forward [k=value] value'– then curvature would just be a parameter of the 'forward' command. And not just that; it could apply to anything that leaves a trace.

During their earlier negotiation and exploration, students used programming commands to design the curved part of their model. At that point, curvature was the outcome of executing commands,

not yet becoming an object of thought (interiorization). In this critical incident, students start again with operational ideas, such as ‘forward’ or ‘degrees’, and through reflection, start to conceptualize curvature as a property: as a noun, not a verb. This moment reflects a process of condensation and emerging reification, where the student has condensed their previous experience (use of the tool and negotiation within the team) into a single, coherent concept. Student A’s remark in 372 indicates that curvature is not only something enacted by turning, but something that exists, a property that can be parameterized. At this stage, students are able to talk about curvature independently of the actions that generated it. This suggests they are approaching reification, beginning to perceive curvature as an entity-object, albeit still relationally linked to motion. It represents an active process of conceptual construction, triggered by the interplay of representations in MaLT2, while student’s statement functions as a gateway toward a structural understanding of the concept. Finally, the idea that curvature could be a general property of *“anything that leaves a trace”* (line 372) implies a shift toward formal generalization, perceiving curvature as a systemic, transferable attribute that can extend beyond the specific task or context.

Figure 1. a. Students’ examples of wind turbine models designed and printed in MaLT2 environment, b. A diagram of the “digital-physical” interplay

Turning to line 371, Student B states that curvature shapes the meaning of 'forward'. Although not in formal mathematical language, this expression conveys a core idea: the rate of change of direction, which lies at the heart of the mathematical concept of curvature. The students link curvature with directional change as an object ‘moves forward’, implying a shift in angle and direction, and essentially connecting curvature to the evolving orientation of the tangent. This association aligns with the way curvature is defined in differential geometry: as the change in direction per unit length. Through symbolic language, inherently tied to the avatar’s current position and next step, students perceive curvature dynamically and locally. As they manipulate values in MaLT2, they observe changes unfolding in real time, reinforcing the idea of curvature as a parameter of motion rather than a static geometric feature. Such reasoning reflects an emerging understanding of rate of change and demonstrates the development of mathematical thinking competency. Student A’s effort to treat curvature as a measurable property indicates the beginning of abstraction. At the same time, Student B's phrasing suggests a personal but conceptually rich representation of curvature, grounded in the semantics of the ‘forward’ command, an inventive use of representation that could evolve into a more formal mathematical conception.

With regard to the theme “Interplay of different representations”, we offer insights into the interaction between digital and physical models that shaped students’ mathematical understanding, actions and competence. Figure 1b highlights a system developed to capture how transitions between digital design and physical 3D printing impacted students’ engagement with mathematics.

The previously discussed incident exemplifies this dynamic interplay. It emerged from students' work with purely **“digital”** representations through coding and dynamically manipulating their models within the MaLT2 environment. However, the thematic analysis also revealed another layer of interaction, which we refer to as the **“phygital”** approach: a hybrid of *physical* and *digital*. This refers to instances where students initiated deeper mathematical discussions starting from their printed models. These moments often led to significant revisions in their digital designs and prompted them to reconceptualize, reinterpret, or apply mathematical ideas in new ways; first discussed by Kynigos and Schiza (2025) as early findings from the 1st cycle of this design-based project. Following the same rationale, the **“digital”** approach refers to transitions from digital to physical. In many cases, students designed models, only to realize that their designs couldn't be printed as intended. This prompted a re-evaluation of their mathematical reasoning, leading to revisions in both their code and physical artifact. Building a final model in MaLT2 required coordination across multiple representations: symbolic (code), graphical (figure), dynamic (manipulation via sliders), and physical (printed object). A key outcome was the emerging need to create generalized procedures with shared variables to manipulate models with greater flexibility and precision, revealing deeper insights into their evolving mathematical thinking and representational competency. For instance, as one student explained: *“At first, sliders helped us create the model. However, this wasn't printable, because changing one part broke everything. We needed something more stable, and we realized that... that was the code. When we made procedures for each part using the same variables, the sliders became less useful for the design—just for confirmation.”* This shift reflects not only movement between representations, but also metacognitive awareness of the function each representation serves. As students built their models, they developed mathematical thinking by connecting parts through generalized hyper-procedures. Crucially, practices such as abstraction and debugging, supported by MaLT2's affordances, shaped and enhanced different aspects of their mathematical competence. Designing curves using procedures, not equations, or *“pixel by pixel”* as one student described it, challenged their understanding, enabling them to explore 3D space and curvature behaviour through assumption, testing and rapid prototyping.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that learners can construct sophisticated mathematical concepts through integrated processes of 3D design, programming, and printing. Students' interpretation of curvature as a property of the 'forward' command reflects a rich mathematical reorientation aligned with its differential geometric definition as a parameter of motion. Their proposal to replace angle manipulation with curvature bridges procedural programming logic and geometric behavior. Importantly, the students' invented language and representations are not incidental; they reflect emerging forms of mathematical reasoning. This type of design-based modeling reveals forms of mathematical competence that arise beyond traditional problem-solving contexts. Notably, students' understanding of curvature and rate of change was not explicitly taught but emerged through the interplay of digital and physical representations. The embodied experience of designing, visualizing, and printing lent concreteness to an otherwise abstract and challenging concept. These results suggest that tool-mediated, design-oriented activities, particularly when coupled with reflective dialogue and learner design agency, can foster deep mathematical insight. The three frameworks of constructionism, reification, and KOM collectively provided a comprehensive lens for our analysis, each capturing a distinct aspect: the design-based construction of meaning and agency,

cognitive shifts from process to object, and the contextual enactment of mathematical competence. Without them, key dimensions of students' engagement with mathematical ideas through MaLT2 would remain unexamined. Future research should further investigate how hybrid digital-physical environments can support students' mathematical competence development in these contexts.

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